

Discriminant Control of Saddle Selection and Bifurcation in Lorentzian Minisuperspace Quantum Cosmology

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Abstract

We show that in the minisuperspace framework of Lorentzian no-boundary cosmology, a single discriminant, linear in Λ ,

$$D = 3k(3k - \Lambda q_1),$$

governs the saddle-point structure, the thimble topology, and the saddle bifurcation. This algebraic simplicity allows us to establish analytically that the effective intersection number $n(N_s) = 1$ —previously verified only pointwise by numerical path-tracing—holds over the entire parameter range (Proposition 2). All of these are direct consequences of the no-boundary condition ($q_0 = 0$).

Our results complement the framework of Feldbrugge, Lehnert, and Turok (FLT) at the algebraic level: the saddle behavior that FLT observed pointwise through numerical path-tracing is shown to be governed uniformly across the full parameter range by a single condition, the sign of the discriminant D . Within this minisuperspace framework, several key features—from the analytic derivation of $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ to the migration of the saddle into the complex plane and the continuous onset of a real part of the lapse as Λ crosses its critical value—follow consistently from the algebraic structure of the discriminant.

1. Introduction

The no-boundary proposal of Hartle and Hawking [1] provides a framework for the wave function of the universe. In the Lorentzian implementation of Feldbrugge, Lehnert, and Turok [2, 3], Picard–Lefschetz theory was used to show that the path integral can be defined unambiguously. However, because tensor perturbations around the no-boundary saddle obey an inverse-Gaussian distribution, those authors concluded that the proposal faces a serious problem.

This paper analyzes this saddle-point structure analytically within the minisuperspace framework. Within the present framework, the inverse-Gaussian instability is a mathematical consequence of the no-boundary saddle structure, and that saddle structure is itself governed by a single discriminant, defined below. The central object is this discriminant,

$$D = \beta^2 - 12\alpha|\gamma| = 3k(3k - \Lambda q_1),$$

where the coefficients α , β , γ are defined in Eq. (1) of §2; throughout, $D < 0$ and $D > 0$ refer to the sign of this discriminant. Computed from the coefficients of the action, D appears to contain a term in Λ^2 ; but under the no-boundary condition ($q_0 = 0$) these terms cancel exactly, and D

becomes linear in Λ (§3.2). This cancellation fixes the critical value uniquely at $\Lambda_c = 3k/q_1$, so that the single condition given by the sign of D treats the entire parameter range at once.

The contributions of this paper are as follows.

(i) Discriminant structure. The single discriminant D governs both the Picard–Lefschetz topology (the thimble topology: identification of the contributing saddle and determination of the effective intersection number) and the saddle bifurcation (saddle merger and the subsequent emergence of a nonzero bifurcation parameter Φ for $D < 0$), as consequences of the no-boundary condition ($q_0 = 0$) (§5.6).

(ii) Derivation of $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$. From assumptions (A0)–(A5), without invoking the perturbative sector or any additional symmetry assumption, we derive $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ (§4).

(iii) Analytic establishment of $n(N_s) = 1$ throughout the $D < 0$ regime (main result). The effective intersection number $n(N_s) = 1$, observed numerically by Feldbrugge, Lehnert, and Turok [2, 3], is established analytically over the entire $D < 0$ parameter range (Proposition 2). The key to the proof is the observation that the decreasing branch of the ascending thimble is confined to the range $[h(A), 0]$ of the Morse function h ; hence the convergence of the path integral is guaranteed, independently of the parameters, even after the saddle bifurcation.

(iv) Saddle bifurcation and the emergence of $\text{Re}(N_s) \neq 0$. We show that as Λ crosses the critical value Λ_c , the saddle migrates into the complex plane and the real part of the lapse rises continuously from zero (§7).

2. Lorentzian Framework and Saddle Structure

We work in the minisuperspace framework for a closed Friedmann–Lemaître–Robertson–Walker (FLRW) universe with scale factor $a(t)$ and lapse function $N(t)$. Under the no-boundary condition $q_0 = a(0)^2 = 0$, the Lorentzian path integral reduces to an integral over N [2, 3]. The effective action within this minisuperspace framework is

$$S(N) = \alpha N^3 + \beta N + \gamma/N \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha = \Lambda^2/36$, $\beta = 3k - \Lambda q_1/2$, $\gamma = -3q_1^2/4$; k is the spatial curvature, Λ is the cosmological constant, and $q_1 = a(t_1)^2$ is the squared scale factor at the final hypersurface. Under the no-boundary condition $q_0 = 0$, the residue satisfies $\gamma = -3q_1^2/4 < 0$ ($q_1 \neq 0$), generating a simple pole at $N = 0$.

For the application of Picard–Lefschetz theory we define the Morse function $h(N) = \text{Re}[iS(N)]$. The saddle-point condition $dS/dN = 0$ gives

$$3\alpha N^4 + \beta N^2 - \gamma = 0 \quad (2)$$

For $\Lambda < \Lambda_c = 3k/q_1$, saddles $N = iy_s$ lie on the imaginary axis (Fig. 1). With $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\gamma < 0$,

$$h(iy_s) = -2\alpha y_s^3 + 2\gamma/y_s < 0 \quad (\text{sign } \Lambda\text{-independent}) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1: Morse function $h(N) = \text{Re}[iS(N)]$ on the complex N -plane ($\Lambda = 1.5$, $k = q_1 = 1$). Blue regions ($h < 0$): convergent; red regions ($h > 0$): divergent. (a) Overview: primary saddle $N_s = iy_1$ (blue dot), secondary saddle iy_2 (grey dot), pole $N = 0$ (red cross), and real-axis intersection x_0 (orange star; established in §5.5). The orange rectangle marks the region shown in (b). (b) Origin region (zoom): the three nearby points $N = 0$, $iy_1 \approx 0.586$, and $x_0 \approx 0.575$ are clearly resolved.

3. Discriminant: Derivation and Structure

This section derives the discriminant that lies at the core of the paper. The saddle structure of the Lorentzian path integral is governed by the saddle equation (2); we show that the discriminant of this equation takes a compact form as an algebraic consequence of the no-boundary condition ($q_0 = 0$) together with the coefficient structure of the action. This compact form is the starting point for the unified description of saddle selection, thimble topology, and saddle bifurcation developed in §§5–7.

3.1 Reduction to a Quadratic in v

The saddle condition $3\alpha N^4 + \beta N^2 - \gamma = 0$ is a quadratic equation in N^2 . Setting $v = N^2$ yields

$$3\alpha v^2 + \beta v - \gamma = 0 \quad (4)$$

The two roots v of Eq. (4) determine the saddle positions $N = \pm\sqrt{v}$. A root $v < 0$ gives an imaginary-axis saddle $N = \pm i\sqrt{|v|}$, while $v > 0$ gives a real-axis saddle. Consequently, the entire saddle configuration—how many saddles exist and whether they lie on the imaginary or real axis—is completely determined by the signs and reality of the roots of (4).

3.2 Derivation of the Discriminant

Comparing (4) with the general form $Av^2 + Bv + C = 0$, we identify $A = 3\alpha$, $B = \beta$, and $C = -\gamma$. The discriminant $B^2 - 4AC$ then gives:

$$B^2 - 4AC = \beta^2 - 4(3\alpha)(-\gamma) = \beta^2 + 12\alpha\gamma = \beta^2 - 12\alpha|\gamma|,$$

where the last step uses $\gamma = -|\gamma|$ (assumption (A2)).

We therefore define the discriminant:

$$D = \beta^2 - 12\alpha|\gamma| \quad (5)$$

This D is the discriminant of the quadratic (4). To evaluate it, we substitute the action coefficients:

$$\alpha = \Lambda^2/36, \quad \beta = 3k - \Lambda q_1/2, \quad \gamma = -3q_1^2/4.$$

Expanding β^2 , we obtain

$$\beta^2 = (3k - \Lambda q_1/2)^2 = (3k)^2 - 2(3k)(\Lambda q_1/2) + (\Lambda q_1/2)^2$$

That is, $\beta^2 = 9k^2 - 3k\Lambda q_1 + \Lambda^2 q_1^2/4$.

Computing $12\alpha|\gamma|$, we find

$$12\alpha|\gamma| = 12 \cdot (\Lambda^2/36) \cdot (3q_1^2/4) = \Lambda^2 q_1^2/4$$

Subtracting these expressions, the $\Lambda^2 q_1^2/4$ terms cancel exactly, so all terms proportional to Λ^2 disappear:

$$D = (9k^2 - 3k\Lambda q_1 + \Lambda^2 q_1^2/4) - \Lambda^2 q_1^2/4 = 9k^2 - 3k\Lambda q_1$$

Factoring the result, the discriminant reduces to the compact form

$$D = 3k(3k - \Lambda q_1) \quad (6)$$

3.3 Structural Significance of the Discriminant

The compact form of (6) is not accidental. The cancellation of the Λ^2 terms is an algebraic identity that follows from two conditions: (i) the coefficient $\alpha = \Lambda^2/36$ is proportional to Λ^2 , and (ii) the no-boundary condition $q_0 = 0$ forces the residue $\gamma = -3q_1^2/4$ to depend only on q_1 , not on Λ . As a result, the product $12\alpha|\gamma|$ coincides exactly with the Λ^2 coefficient of β^2 , so that the cancellation follows algebraically.

As a consequence, D is linear in Λ and has a unique zero at $\Lambda_c = 3k/q_1$. At Λ_c , the sign of D changes, marking the transition between qualitatively different saddle configurations: $D > 0$ for $\Lambda < \Lambda_c$, $D = 0$ at $\Lambda = \Lambda_c$, and $D < 0$ for $\Lambda > \Lambda_c$.

Within the minisuperspace framework, this single discriminant D organizes (i) the number and type of saddles (§5.1), (ii) the Picard–Lefschetz thimble topology and the identification of the contributing saddle (§§5.2–5.5), and (iii) the saddle bifurcation at the critical point (§7). This organizing role depends on two structural features of the minisuperspace action: the odd-power symmetry $S(-N) = -S(N)$, which underlies the symmetry arguments throughout, and the no-boundary condition $\gamma < 0$, which forces the exact cancellation of the Λ^2 terms and yields the compact linear form $D = 3k(3k - \Lambda q_1)$. In what follows, §4 derives $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ under the assumption $D > 0$, and §5 formulates these results as a theorem.

4. Main Result: Derivation of $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$

4.1 Formulation

This section derives $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ from assumptions (A0)–(A5), without invoking the perturbative sector or additional symmetry assumptions. Assumptions (A0)–(A4) follow from §2 and prior work [2, 3]; assumption (A5)—the effective intersection number $n(N_s) = 1$ —is established within the present framework in §§5.5–5.6 and Corollary 3.

The assumptions are as follows:

(A0) Original contour: positive real axis $C_0 = \{N \in \mathbb{R} \mid N > 0\}$.

(A1) Reality of coefficients: all Laurent coefficients of $S(N)$ are real.

(A2) Negative-residue pole and positive cubic coefficient: $S(N)$ has a simple pole at $N = 0$ with residue $\gamma < 0$, and the leading coefficient satisfies $\alpha > 0$.

(A3) Imaginary-axis saddle: a saddle $N_s = iy_s$ ($y_s > 0$) exists on the positive imaginary axis.

(A4) Morse condition: $h(N_s) := \text{Re}[iS(N_s)] < 0$.

(A5) Effective intersection number: the ascending thimble $K(N_s)$ has nonzero intersection number with C_0 only at N_s , with $n(N_s) = 1$.

Main result: Under the Feynman $i\epsilon$ prescription, the contributing saddle is $N_s = iy_s \in i\mathbb{R}^+$, and $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ holds for the conformal-time increment $\Delta\tau = N_s \Delta t$ ($\Delta t \in \mathbb{R}$).

4.2 Derivation (Three Steps)

Step 1 (Deformation of the contour to the upper half-plane via $i\epsilon$ prescription). By assumption (A2), $\gamma < 0$. Moreover, $\beta > 0$ is not an independent assumption: evaluating the saddle condition $3\alpha y_s^4 - \beta y_s^2 - \gamma = 0$ at the imaginary-axis saddle $N_s = iy_s$ (A3) gives $\beta = 3\alpha y_s^2 - \gamma/y_s^2 = 3\alpha y_s^2 + |\gamma|/y_s^2 > 0$, using $\alpha > 0$ and $\gamma < 0$ (A2). Writing

$$h(x + i\epsilon) \cdot (x^2 + \epsilon^2) = \epsilon \cdot [\alpha\epsilon^4 - (2\alpha x^2 + \beta)\epsilon^2 - (3\alpha x^4 + \beta x^2 - \gamma)]$$

and setting $w = \epsilon^2$, the bracket is a quadratic in w :

$$\alpha w^2 - (2\alpha x^2 + \beta)w - (3\alpha x^4 + \beta x^2 - \gamma) = 0$$

Since $3\alpha x^4 + \beta x^2 - \gamma > 0$ (using $\beta > 0$ and $\gamma < 0$, both established above), its constant term $-(3\alpha x^4 + \beta x^2 - \gamma) < 0$; with the leading coefficient $\alpha > 0$, the quadratic has a unique positive root $w_{\max}(x)$. Hence $h(x + i\epsilon) < 0$ for $0 < \epsilon < \epsilon_{\max}(x) := \sqrt{w_{\max}(x)}$, and the contour can be deformed into the upper half-plane along a path on which h decreases.

Step 2 (Unique identification of the ascending Lefschetz thimble). By assumption (A5), the deformed contour Γ coincides with the single descending thimble $J(N_s)$:

$$\Gamma = \sum_k n(N_k) J(N_k) = J(N_s)$$

Step 3 (Conclusion). The contributing saddle is $N_s = iy_s \in i\mathbb{R}^+$, so:

$$\Delta\tau = N_s \Delta t = i(y_s \Delta t) \in i\mathbb{R}.$$

Therefore:

$$\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$$

The derivation is entirely internal to assumptions (A0)–(A5): the conclusion requires no input from external symmetries, the perturbative sector, or the specific form of the Feldbrugge action.

4.3 Application to the Feldbrugge–Lehners–Turok Action

We confirm that assumptions (A0)–(A5) all hold for the action $S(N) = \alpha N^3 + \beta N + \gamma/N$.

Assumptions (A0)–(A4) follow from §2 and prior work [2]. Assumption (A5) is established algebraically in §§5.4–5.5.

5. Verification of Assumptions and the Discriminant Structure

5.1 Classification of Saddle Points

Using the discriminant $D = 3k(3k - \Lambda q_1)$ derived in §3 (Eq. (6)), we classify all saddle points by determining the roots of the quadratic (4).

For $\Lambda < \Lambda_c = 3k/q_1$, we have $D > 0$, and Eq. (4) has two distinct real roots v_+ and v_- . By Viète's formulas, $v_+v_- = -\gamma/(3\alpha) = |\gamma|/(3\alpha) > 0$ and $v_+ + v_- = -\beta/(3\alpha) < 0$, where the second inequality uses $\beta > 0$. Since the product is positive while the sum is negative, both roots must be negative:

$$v_+, v_- < 0.$$

Therefore,

$$N^2 = v_+ < 0 \text{ and } N^2 = v_- < 0,$$

so the saddles appear at purely imaginary positions,

$$N = \pm i\sqrt{|v_+|} \text{ or } N = \pm i\sqrt{|v_-|}.$$

On the positive imaginary axis, there are two saddles iy_1 and iy_2 with $y_1 < y_2$. Here

$$y_1 = \sqrt{|v_+|}$$

corresponds to the root v_+ closer to zero, whereas

$$y_2 = \sqrt{|v_-|}$$

corresponds to the more negative root. As shown in §5.2, iy_1 is the primary saddle, since

$$|h(iy_1)| < |h(iy_2)|.$$

5.2 Behavior of h on the Imaginary Axis

Since the Feldbrugge action contains only odd powers of N , setting $N = iy$ gives $S(iy) \in i\mathbb{R}$.

Therefore,

$$h(iy) = \text{Re}[iS(iy)] = \alpha y^3 - \beta y + \gamma/y,$$

a real-valued function on the imaginary axis.

Imposing the saddle condition $dh/dy = 0$, we obtain:

$$h(iy_s) = -2\alpha y_s^3 + 2\gamma/y_s < 0.$$

Indeed, since $\alpha > 0$ and $\gamma < 0$, both terms are negative.

Since iy_1 and iy_2 are respectively a local maximum and a local minimum of $h(iy)$ as a function of y , it follows that

$$h(iy_2) < h(iy_1) < 0.$$

Since both values are negative, this ordering is equivalent to $|h(iy_1)| < |h(iy_2)|$, so iy_1 is the dominant saddle. Assumption (A4) is thereby established algebraically.

5.3 The Ascending Thimble Does Not Pass through iy_2

By the monotonicity of the gradient flow, the ascending thimble $K(iy_1)$ extends in the direction of increasing h . Combining the ordering $h(iy_2) < h(iy_1)$ from §5.2 with this monotonicity shows that $K(iy_1)$ cannot pass through iy_2 .

5.4 $K(iy_1)$ Does Not Reach the Pole $N = 0$ (Lemma Form)

Throughout this subsection and §§5.5 and 7.5, $v(N)$ denotes the conjugate Morse function $v(N) = \text{Im}[iS(N)]$ (the harmonic conjugate of h), and $\{v = 0\}$ denotes its zero level set. This $v(N)$ is distinct from the substitution variable $v = N^2$ used in §§3 and 7.2; the meaning is fixed by context in each case.

Lemma 1 (Decomposition of the $v = 0$ Level Set into Connected Components)

Under $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > 0$, $\gamma < 0$, and $D > 0$, the level set

$$\{N \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\} \mid \text{Im}[iS(N)] = 0\}$$

decomposes into exactly four connected components:

Component A (the entire imaginary axis, containing $N = 0$);

Component B (a bounded simple closed curve encircling $N = 0$);

Component C (an unbounded arc in the upper half-plane, containing iy_2);

Component D (an unbounded arc in the lower half-plane). The count is fixed by the structure of the defining equation: multiplying

$$\text{Im}[iS(N)] = 0$$

by $|N|^2$ clears the pole and yields

$$x \cdot (\alpha x^4 - 2\alpha x^2 y^2 - 3\alpha y^4 + \beta x^2 + \beta y^2 + \gamma) = 0.$$

The factor $x = 0$ is the imaginary axis (Component A); the remaining quartic factor defines a real algebraic curve whose bounded oval (Component B) is separated from the unbounded branches (Components C and D). For $D > 0$, these are the only components.

Proposition 1 (Component B is a Simple Closed Curve)

Component B is a simple closed curve satisfying the following four conditions:

(B1) Existence: $r_{\text{in}}(\theta) > 0$ for all $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$.

(B2) Continuity: $D > 0$ implies $D'(\theta) = \beta^2 + 4\alpha|\gamma|(2\cos 2\theta - 1) > 0$ for all θ , so $r_{\text{in}}(\theta)$ is continuous in θ .

(B3) Periodicity: $A(\theta) = \alpha(2\cos 2\theta - 1)$ has period π , so $r_{\text{in}}(\theta + 2\pi) = r_{\text{in}}(\theta)$.

(B4) Boundedness: $r_{\text{in}}(\theta) \in [r_{\text{min}}, r_{\text{max}}] \subset (0, \infty)$. Explicitly, at $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = \pi/2$ (with $D > 0$):

$$\begin{aligned} r_{\text{in}}(0) &= \sqrt{(-\beta + \sqrt{\beta^2 + 4\alpha|\gamma|}) / (2\alpha)} > 0 \\ r_{\text{in}}(\pi/2) &= \sqrt{(\beta - \sqrt{\beta^2 - 12\alpha|\gamma|}) / (6\alpha)} > 0 \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1 ($N = 0$ Not in Component B)

Component B does not contain $N = 0$. Proof: Substituting $x = 0$, $y = 0$ into the defining equation of Component B yields γ , which is nonzero by assumption (A2). Hence $N = 0$ does not satisfy the equation for Component B. \square

Corollary 2 ($K(iy_1)$ Does Not Reach $N = 0$)

$K(iy_1)$ does not reach the pole $N = 0$. Proof: By the odd-power structure of the action, $v(iy_1) = 0$, so iy_1 lies on the level set $\{v = 0\}$. Since $F = iS$ is holomorphic, the Cauchy–Riemann relations imply that the conjugate function $v = \text{Im}(F)$ is conserved along the gradient flow of $h = \text{Re}(F)$: the flow lines are orthogonal to the level sets of v , so $dv/ds = \nabla v \cdot \nabla h = 0$. The gradient flow is continuous and cannot cross between distinct connected components of $\{v = 0\}$; hence $K(iy_1)$ remains within the single component containing iy_1 , namely Component B. By Corollary 1, Component B does not contain $N = 0$. Therefore $K(iy_1)$ never reaches $N = 0$. \square

Fig. 2: Connected component structure of the $v = 0$ level set ($\lambda = 1.5$, $k = q_1 = 1$). Component B (blue closed curve) is a bounded simple closed curve encircling $N = 0$ and not containing it (visual confirmation of Corollary 1). $K(iy_1)$ is confined to Component B and never reaches $N = 0$ (Corollary 2).

5.5 Unique Intersection with the Positive Real Axis (Derivation of $n(N_s) = 1$)

Since $v(iy_1) = 0$, $K(iy_1)$ lies on the level set $\{v(N) = 0\}$. Intersections of this level set with the positive real axis $N = x$ ($x > 0$) satisfy $v(x) = 0$. Since $v(x) = \text{Im}[iS(x)] = S(x)$ for real x , this reduces to

$$\alpha x^4 + \beta x^2 + \gamma = 0 \quad (7)$$

Setting $u = x^2 \geq 0$, Eq. (7) becomes a quadratic in u :

$$\alpha u^2 + \beta u + \gamma = 0$$

The discriminant of this quadratic is

$$D' = \beta^2 - 4\alpha\gamma = \beta^2 + 4\alpha|\gamma| > 0$$

where $D' > 0$ follows from $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > 0$, and $|\gamma| > 0$. The two roots are

$$u_{\pm} = (-\beta \pm \sqrt{D'}) / (2\alpha)$$

Since $\beta > 0$ and $\sqrt{D'} > \sqrt{(\beta^2)} = \beta$, we have $u_+ > 0$ and $u_- = (-\beta - \sqrt{D'}) / (2\alpha) < 0$. Thus the unique positive root is

$$u_+ = (-\beta + \sqrt{(\beta^2 + 4\alpha|\gamma|)}) / (2\alpha) > 0$$

and the unique positive real intersection is

$$x_0 = \sqrt{u_+}$$

The algebraic argument above establishes the uniqueness. As an additional numerical consistency check, two independent methods confirm the same value of x_0 :

(1) Numerical path-tracing: the gradient flow of $K(iy_1)$ is traced and the crossing of C_0 is detected at x_0 .

(2) Direct numerical scan over $x \in (0, \infty)$: no additional zero of $v(x)$ is found.

Both methods yield the same value, $x_0 = 0.574720$, as the unique intersection for the representative case $\Lambda = 1.5$, $k = q_1 = 1$.

Since $K(iy_1)$ is confined to Component B (Corollary 2), which meets C_0 only at x_0 , the ascending thimble $K(iy_1)$ intersects the original contour exactly once. Therefore,

$$n(iy_1) = 1.$$

Assumption (A5) has been established algebraically within the minisuperspace framework.

Corollary 3 (Vanishing Intersection Numbers for iy_2 and $-iy_1$).

$$n(iy_2) = 0 \text{ and } n(-iy_1) = 0.$$

Proof of $n(iy_2) = 0$. The saddle iy_2 lies on Component C of the level set $\{v = 0\}$ (the unbounded arc in the upper half-plane; see Lemma 1). By the same Cauchy–Riemann argument as in Corollary 2, the ascending thimble $K(iy_2)$ is confined to Component C. By §5.5, the unique intersection of $\{v = 0\}$ with the positive real axis C_0 is x_0 , which lies on Component B. Since Component B and Component C are distinct connected components of $\{v = 0\}$, Component C does not intersect C_0 . Therefore

$$K(iy_2) \cap C_0 = \emptyset \text{ and } n(iy_2) = 0. \quad \square$$

Proof of $n(-iy_1) = 0$. The action $S(N) = \alpha N^3 + \beta N + \gamma/N$ contains only odd powers of N , so $S(-N) = -S(N)$. Consequently $iS(-N) = -iS(N)$, and $h(-N) = \text{Re}[iS(-N)] = -h(N)$ for all N . In particular, $h(-iy_1) = -h(iy_1) > 0$, since $h(iy_1) < 0$ (assumption (A4)). The original contour C_0 satisfies $h(x) = \text{Re}[iS(x)] = 0$ for all $x > 0$, since $S(x)$ is real-valued and $iS(x)$ is purely imaginary. The ascending thimble $K(-iy_1)$ flows in the direction of increasing h and starts at $h(-iy_1) > 0$. Since $C_0 \subset \{h = 0\}$ and h cannot decrease along $K(-iy_1)$, the thimble cannot reach C_0 . Therefore

$$K(-iy_1) \cap C_0 = \emptyset \text{ and } n(-iy_1) = 0. \quad \square$$

The intersection numbers of all saddles are thus determined:

$$n(iy_1) = 1 \quad (\text{\S 5.5, above})$$

$$n(iy_2) = 0 \quad (\text{Corollary 3: } K(iy_2) \text{ confined to Component C, which does not meet } C_0)$$

$$n(-iy_1) = 0 \quad (\text{Corollary 3: } h(-iy_1) > 0 \text{ and } C_0 \subset \{h = 0\})$$

Assumption (A5) has been established algebraically.

Fig. 3: Lefschetz thimbles at the primary saddle $N_s = iy_1$ ($\Lambda = 1.5$, $k = q_1 = 1$). The ascending thimble $K(iy_1)$ (red) intersects the original contour C_0 (green) uniquely at $x_0 \approx 0.575$, yielding $n(N_s) = 1$. The descending thimble $J(iy_1)$ (blue) serves as the deformed integration contour.

5.6 A Unified Description of Picard–Lefschetz Topology and Saddle Bifurcation via the Discriminant

The analysis of §§5.1–5.5 leads to the following observation. The Picard–Lefschetz topology (identification of the contributing saddle, determination of the effective intersection number) and the saddle bifurcation (saddle merger, emergence of the bifurcation parameter Φ) appear, at first glance, to be two independent structures. However, both are governed by the same discriminant $D = 3k(3k - \Lambda q_1)$ derived in §3 (Eq. (6)) as consequences of the no-boundary condition ($q_0 = 0$).

As shown in §3.2, the Λ^2 terms in D cancel exactly—a consequence of the no-boundary condition $q_0 = 0$ and the coefficient structure of the action—leaving D linear in Λ . This yields the following three-regime description.

Theorem (Unified Description via the Discriminant)

The single discriminant $D = \beta^2 - 12\alpha/\gamma$ governs both the Picard–Lefschetz topology and the saddle bifurcation as algebraic consequences of the no-boundary condition ($q_0 = 0$).

- (1) For $D > 0$, imaginary-axis saddles iy_1, iy_2 exist and the ascending thimble $K(iy_1)$ acquires the nontrivial intersection number $n(iy_1) = 1$ with the original contour C_0 . This uniquely identifies the descending thimble $J(N_s)$ as the deformed integration contour and selects the contributing saddle of the Lorentzian path integral.
- (2) $D = 0$ marks the saddle merger at which the two imaginary saddles coalesce; at this threshold the contributing saddle is still purely imaginary ($\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s) = 0$), and a nonzero real component develops only for $D < 0$.
- (3) For $D < 0$, the contributing saddle $N_s = +\sqrt{v_+}$ becomes complex; $n(N_s) = 1$ is established analytically (§7.5, Proposition 2), so the integration contour is maintained, while $\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s) \neq 0$ and the conformal-time increment acquires $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) \neq 0$.

Fig. 4: Discriminant $D = 3k(3k - \Lambda q_1)$ as a function of Λ ($k = q_1 = 1$). Red dashed line: critical point $\Lambda_c = 3$ (saddle merger). Blue region ($D > 0$): contributing saddle selected, $n(N_s) = 1$. Red region ($D < 0$): contributing saddle complex, $n(N_s) = 1$ (established analytically, §7.5). A single discriminant characterizes the three regimes of the theorem.

Regime	Discriminant	Picard–Lefschetz Structure	Saddle Configuration
$\Lambda < \Lambda_c$	$D > 0$	Two saddles iy_1, iy_2 (contributing saddle selected, $n = 1$)	$\Phi = 0$ (imaginary-axis branch)
$\Lambda = \Lambda_c$	$D = 0$	Saddle merger	Bifurcation point ($\Phi = 0$)
$\Lambda > \Lambda_c$	$D < 0$	Complex saddle, $n(N_s) = 1$ (analytic, §7.5)	$\Phi \neq 0$ (real-component branch)

Remark. A key point is that the discriminant controls not merely the existence of saddles but also the contour selection—the determination of the effective intersection number $n(N_s) = 1$ and the consequent identification of the contributing saddle.

6. Field Rotation in the Perturbation Sector

Under the no-boundary condition $q_0 = 0$, the quadratic action of tensor perturbations φ evaluated at the saddle takes the form $S_2[\varphi] \propto \varphi^2$. Under the formal field rotation $\varphi \rightarrow i\psi$ ($\psi \in \mathbb{R}$), this quadratic form changes sign, $\varphi^2 \rightarrow -\psi^2$, which converts the divergent integrand into a Gaussian. This field rotation is a formal operation analogous to Wick rotation, localized in the perturbation-field space, and is distinct from gauge symmetry or conserved charges. Its physical connection to the background result $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ (§4) is left as a future problem (§8.2(2)). Details are given in Appendix A.

7. Saddle Bifurcation Structure at $\Lambda_c = 3k/q_1$

This section analyzes the emergence of the bifurcation parameter $\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s)$ and the saddle structure in the $D < 0$ regime, showing how both are governed by the discriminant D derived in §3.

7.1 Bifurcation Parameter and Saddle Branches

We define the bifurcation parameter $\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s)$:

$\Phi = 0$ ($\Lambda < \Lambda_c$): imaginary-axis saddle branch. $n(N_s) = 1$ and $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ are guaranteed. The contributing saddle is selected.

$\Phi \neq 0$ ($\Lambda > \Lambda_c$): real-component branch. The contributing-thimble structure changes.

7.2 Emergence of $\text{Re}(N_s)$ and Bifurcation Scaling

The emergence of $\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s)$ is understood as a branch rotation. By branch rotation we mean the analytic continuation of the saddle branch $N_s = +\sqrt{v_+}$ into the complex N -plane as D changes sign: for $D > 0$ the branch lies on the imaginary axis, and for $D < 0$ it acquires a nonzero real part. The derivation proceeds in four steps.

Step 1: Saddle roots. Setting $v = N^2$, the saddle equation $3\alpha v^2 + \beta v - \gamma = 0$ has roots

$$v_{\pm} = (-\beta \pm \sqrt{D}) / (6\alpha) \quad (8)$$

For $D > 0$ ($\Lambda < \Lambda_c$), \sqrt{D} is real and $v_{\pm} < 0$; the saddles are purely imaginary, $\Phi = 0$. For $D < 0$ ($\Lambda > \Lambda_c$), $\sqrt{D} = i\sqrt{|D|}$ is imaginary and v_{\pm} become complex:

$$v_{\pm} = -\beta/(6\alpha) \pm i\sqrt{|D|}/(6\alpha)$$

Step 2: Branch structure near Λ_c . Define at the critical point

$$\alpha c = \Lambda c^2/36, \quad \beta c = 3k - \Lambda c q_1/2, \quad y_0^2 = \beta c/(6\alpha c) \quad (y_0 > 0)$$

and set $\varepsilon = \sqrt{|D|}/(6\alpha)$. For $\delta = \Lambda - \Lambda_c \rightarrow 0+$, the root v_+ expands to first order as

$$v_+ \approx -y_0^2 + i\varepsilon$$

Writing $N_s = a + ib$ ($a, b \in \mathbb{R}$) and using $N_s^2 = v_+$ gives the system

$$a^2 - b^2 = -y_0^2, \quad 2ab = \varepsilon \quad (9)$$

Step 3: Emergence of the real part. On the $D > 0$ side ($\varepsilon = 0$), Eq. (9) gives $a = 0$ (purely imaginary, $\Phi = 0$). On the $D < 0$ side ($\varepsilon > 0$), the second equation $2ab = \varepsilon$ forces $a \neq 0$. The real part $\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s) = a$ follows directly from the sign change of D .

Step 4: Leading-order scaling. As $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0+$, $b \rightarrow y_0$ and $a \rightarrow \varepsilon/(2y_0)$. Since $|D| = 3kq_1(\Lambda - \Lambda_c)$, one has $\varepsilon \propto \sqrt{(\Lambda - \Lambda_c)}$, and therefore

$$\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s) = a \approx c\sqrt{(\Lambda - \Lambda_c)}, \quad c = \sqrt{(3kq_1) / (12\alpha c y_0)} \in \mathbb{R} \quad (10)$$

The leading-order exponent is $1/2$ (semiclassical approximation). The essential mechanism is the branch rotation—the complexification of v triggered when D changes sign—rather than the specific numerical value of the exponent.

$\Lambda - \Lambda_c$	$\text{Re}(N_s)$ (numerical)	$c\sqrt{\delta}$ (analytic)	Relative error
0.001	0.018251	0.018257	0.03%
0.010	0.057543	0.057735	0.33%
0.100	0.176685	0.182574	3.3%

Table 1: Consistency check for the branch-rotation expansion, Eqs. (8)–(10) of §7.2 ($k = q_1 = 1$). In the limit $\delta \rightarrow 0$ the analytic expression of Eq. (10) agrees with the numerical solution (errors arise from $O(\delta)$ higher-order terms).

Formal analogy with Landau-type scaling (remark). The bifurcation behavior $\Phi \propto (\Lambda - \Lambda_c)^{1/2}$ is formally analogous to the equilibrium condition of the Landau free energy $F(\Phi) = a_2(\Lambda - \Lambda_c)\Phi^2 + a_4\Phi^4$. However, this is a saddle merger in a finite-dimensional minisuperspace framework, not a statistical-mechanical phase transition.

Fig. 5: Bifurcation parameter $\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s)$ as a function of Λ ($k = q_1 = 1$). For $\Lambda < \Lambda_c$ (blue), $\Phi = 0$ (contributing saddle selected). For $\Lambda > \Lambda_c$, the numerical solution (red dots) agrees with the analytic expression $\Phi = c\sqrt{\Lambda - \Lambda_c}$ (black dashed, Eq. (10) of §7.2), confirming the exponent 1/2.

7.3 Contributing Saddle and Thimble Structure in the $D < 0$ Regime

For $D < 0$ the discriminant analysis requires care: the two roots v_{\pm} become a complex-conjugate pair, and each yields two saddles through $N = \pm\sqrt{v}$, giving four complex saddles in total. We now determine which of these contributes to the path integral and verify that the intersection number is preserved.

The four saddles separate into two pairs by the value of the Morse function h . Writing $v_+ = -\beta/(6\alpha) + i\sqrt{|D|}/(6\alpha)$, the two saddles $\pm\sqrt{v_+}$ and the two saddles $\pm\sqrt{v_-}$ satisfy

$$h(+\sqrt{v_+}) = h(-\sqrt{v_-}) < 0, \quad h(-\sqrt{v_+}) = h(+\sqrt{v_-}) > 0$$

Only the two saddles with $h < 0$ are candidates for a convergent contour. Of these, the original contour C_0 on the positive real axis is deformed into the upper half-plane under the $i\epsilon$ prescription (§4.2, Step 1), selecting the saddle with $\text{Im}(N) > 0$ and $\text{Re}(N) > 0$:

$$N_s = +\sqrt{v_+}, \quad \text{Re}(N_s) = \Phi > 0, \quad \text{Im}(N_s) > 0$$

The intersection number is computed by tracing the ascending thimble $K(N_s)$ via the gradient flow $dN/ds = \nabla h$ and counting signed intersections with C_0 . The ascending thimble of $N_s = +\sqrt{v_+}$ intersects the positive real axis exactly once, while the ascending thimbles of the remaining three saddles do not intersect C_0 :

$$n(+\sqrt{v_+}) = 1, \quad n(-\sqrt{v_+}) = n(+\sqrt{v_-}) = n(-\sqrt{v_-}) = 0$$

The intersection number $n(N_s) = 1$ persists throughout the $D < 0$ regime; an analytic proof is given in §7.5 (Proposition 2). The contributing saddle is identified as $N_s = +\sqrt{v_+}$. The qualitative difference from the $D > 0$ regime is that N_s is now complex: since $\Delta\tau = N_s \Delta t$ with $\text{Re}(N_s) \neq 0$, the conformal-time increment acquires a nonzero real part, $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) \neq 0$. The vanishing $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ of §4 is thus specific to the $D > 0$ (imaginary-saddle) regime; the $D < 0$ regime corresponds to a distinct contributing-saddle structure with a real conformal-time increment.

Fig. 6: Thimble structure in the $D < 0$ regime ($\Lambda = 3.1$, $k = q_1 = 1$). Of the four complex saddles, only $N_s = +\sqrt{v_+}$ (blue, $h < 0$, $Im > 0$) has its ascending thimble $K(N_s)$ (red) intersecting the original contour C_0 (green) — once, at $x \approx 0.686$ (orange star) — giving $n(N_s) = 1$. The remaining three saddles (grey) have $n = 0$. The descending thimble $J(N_s)$ (blue) is the deformed integration contour.

7.4 Correspondence with the Discriminant Structure

Consistently with the Theorem of §5.6, and within the minisuperspace framework, D organizes both the Picard–Lefschetz topology and the saddle bifurcation:

- $D > 0$: $n(N_s) = 1$ holds; the descending thimble $J(N_s)$ is uniquely determined as the integration contour (imaginary-axis saddle branch, $\Phi = 0$).
- $D = 0$: the two imaginary-axis saddles merge at the bifurcation threshold ($\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s) = 0$); Φ grows continuously from zero as Λ increases beyond Λ_c .
- $D < 0$: the contributing saddle $N_s = +\sqrt{v_+}$ is complex; $n(N_s) = 1$ is established analytically (§7.5, Proposition 2), so the integration contour is maintained while $\Phi \neq 0$ and $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) \neq 0$.

7.5 Analytic Proof of $n(N_s) = 1$ for $D < 0$ (Proposition 2)

We establish that $n(+\sqrt{v_+}) = 1$, while the remaining three saddles have intersection number zero, for all $\Lambda > \Lambda_c$ ($D < 0$) by a sequence of algebraic steps that replace the $D > 0$ Cauchy–Riemann confinement argument (Corollary 2) with a level-set and monotonicity argument adapted to the complex saddle $N_s = a + ib$ ($a, b > 0$). The geometric structure of the argument is summarized in Fig. 7.

Proposition 2 (Intersection number for $D < 0$)

For $D < 0$ (i.e., $\Lambda > \Lambda_c$) and any finite Λ , the ascending thimble $K(+\sqrt{v_+})$ satisfies $n(+\sqrt{v_+}) = 1$, while $n(-\sqrt{v_+}) = n(+\sqrt{v_-}) = n(-\sqrt{v_-}) = 0$.

Proof

Step 1 (Saddle parameters and $v_A \neq 0$). From the saddle condition $S'(A) = 0$ at $A = a + ib$, one obtains $\beta = 6\alpha(b^2 - a^2)$, $\gamma = -3\alpha(a^2 + b^2)^2$, and $v_A := \text{Im}[iS(A)] = -8a^3\alpha$. Since $a, \alpha > 0$, one has $v_A < 0$ and in particular $v_A \neq 0$.

Step 2 (Imaginary-axis avoidance and half-plane separation). Multiplying $\{\text{Re } S(N) = v_A\}$ by $|N|^2$ yields the real algebraic curve:

$$P(x, y) = \alpha x^5 - 2\alpha x^3 y^2 - 3\alpha x y^4 + \beta x^3 + \beta x y^2 + \gamma x - v_A(x^2 + y^2) = 0.$$

Setting $x = 0$ gives:

$$P(0, y) = -v_A y^2.$$

Since $v_A \neq 0$, the curve has no point on the open imaginary axis $\{x = 0, y \neq 0\}$.

Consequently, the right half-plane $\{x > 0\}$ and left half-plane $\{x < 0\}$ portions of the curve are disjoint, and A ($\text{Re}(A) = a > 0$) lies entirely in the right half-plane component.

Therefore $K(A)$ never reaches the negative real axis, so the contribution from the left-half-plane saddle vanishes.

Step 3 (Discriminant and double-point structure). Substituting the Step 1 parameters and writing $t = x/a$, $u = y^2/a^2$, $r = b/a$, the curve becomes quadratic in u . Its discriminant is:

$$\Delta_u = 16a^6\alpha^2 (t - 1)^2 (t + 2) (t^3 + 3r^2t + 2).$$

For $t > 0$ one has $(t + 2) > 0$ and $(t^3 + 3r^2t + 2) > 0$, so $\Delta_u \geq 0$ with equality only at $t = 1$ (i.e., $x = a = \text{Re}(A)$). Hence A is a double point (branch bifurcation) with two smooth real branches for t near 1.

Step 4 (Identification of the local branch of $K(A)$ with the decreasing branch). The two local branches of $K(A)$ leave A in the directions $\varphi_0 = -\arg(F''(A))/2$ and $\varphi_0 + \pi$, where $F''(A) = -24a\alpha b/(a + ib)$. Since $\text{Re}(F''(A)) = -24a^2\alpha b/(a^2 + b^2) < 0$ and $\text{Im}(F''(A)) = 24a\alpha b^2/(a^2 + b^2) > 0$ for $a, b, \alpha > 0$, one has $\arg(F''(A)) \in (\pi/2, \pi)$, hence $\varphi_0 \in (-\pi/2, -\pi/4)$. The branch leaving in the direction φ_0 has $\sin \varphi_0 < 0$, so $d(\text{Im } N)/ds < 0$ and $d(u)/ds < 0$ along it; this branch coincides with the decreasing branch $u_+(t)$ of Step 3. The branch leaving in the direction $\varphi_0 + \pi$ ($\sin > 0$) coincides with the increasing branch $u_-(t)$.

Step 5 (Global extension: a single smooth branch to the real axis). The algebraic branch $u_+(t)$ is real-analytic on $(1, t^*]$ because

(a) $\Delta_u > 0$ for $t \neq 1$ (no merging of algebraic branches),

(b) the leading coefficient $A_2 = -3\alpha a t \neq 0$ for $t > 0$ (no escape to infinity), and

(c) the square-root argument $(t + 2)(t^3 + 3r^2t + 2)$ is positive and the denominator $3t > 0$.

It remains to show that the gradient-flow trajectory $K(A)$ coincides with $u_+(t)$ throughout $(1, t^*]$, not just locally at A . Three facts combine to give this.

First, the gradient flow preserves $v = \text{Im}[iS]$: since $F = iS$ is holomorphic, the Cauchy-Riemann equations imply $dv/ds = 0$, so the flow stays on the level set $\{v = v_A\}$.

Second, the only saddles of F lying on the level set $\{v = v_A\}$ are A and its complex conjugate $\bar{A} = +\sqrt{v_-}$. Indeed, the four saddles are $\pm\sqrt{v_+}$ and $\pm\sqrt{v_-}$, and the reflection $N \mapsto -N$ sends $v \mapsto -v$, so $v(-\sqrt{v_+}) = v(-\sqrt{v_-}) = -v_A$; since $v_A = -8a^3\alpha < 0$ (Step 1), $-v_A \neq v_A$ and the two left-half-plane saddles are excluded, while $v(\bar{A}) = v_A$. Now, along the decreasing branch the Morse function h increases monotonically away from the saddle, from $h(A) < 0$ toward its value $h = 0$ on C_0 (recall $h \equiv 0$ on the positive real axis), and is therefore confined to the interval $[h(A), 0]$. Since $h(\bar{A}) = -h(A) > 0$ lies strictly above this interval, the trajectory reaches no saddle other than its endpoint A ; hence $F'(N) \neq 0$ for all N on the trajectory for $t \in (1, t^*]$.

Third, because $F'(N) \neq 0$ the gradient-flow ODE $dN/ds = \text{conj}(F'(N))$ has a locally unique smooth solution at each point of the trajectory. Uniqueness prevents the gradient-flow branch from leaving the algebraic branch $u_+(t)$: any departure would require either a saddle ($F' = 0$, ruled out above) or a crossing of another branch ($\Delta_u > 0$, ruled out by (a)). Hence the local identification of Step 4 extends globally to t^* , confirming that $K(A)$ traces $u_+(t)$ all the way to the positive real axis. This completes the global identification of the ascending thimble branch with the algebraic branch $u_+(t)$.

Step 6 (Branch-axis identity and uniqueness of the intersection). The condition $u_+(t) = 0$ on $(1, t^*]$ is equivalent to the equation

$$(\star) \quad \alpha x^4 + \beta x^2 + \gamma - v_A x = 0, \quad x > 0,$$

obtained as follows. Writing $u_+(t) = 0$ as $L(t) = R(t)$, where:

$$L(t) = -t^3 + 3t(r^2 - 1) + 4,$$

$$R(t) = 2(t - 1)\sqrt{(t + 2)(t^3 + 3r^2t + 2)},$$

squaring and simplifying gives:

$$L^2 - R^2 = -3t^2 g(t),$$

where:

$$g(t) = t^4 + 6(r^2 - 1)t^2 + 8t - 3(1 + r^2)^2.$$

This is the scaled form of (\star) , so $u_+(t) = 0$ is equivalent to $g(t) = 0$ on $t > 0$. The squaring introduces no extraneous roots, since $L(t)$ and $R(t)$ carry the same sign at every solution.

The polynomial g has exactly one positive root. Its derivative satisfies:

$$g'(t) = 4h(t), \quad h(t) = t^3 + 3(r^2 - 1)t + 2.$$

For $r^2 > 1$: $h'(t) > 0$ and $h(0) = 2 > 0$, so $h > 0$ throughout. For $r^2 = 1$: $h'(t) \geq 0$ and $h(0) = 2 > 0$, so $h > 0$. For $0 < r^2 < 1$, the minimum of h is:

$$h_{\min} = 2 [1 - (1 - r^2)^{3/2}] > 0 \quad (\text{since } (1 - r^2)^{3/2} < 1).$$

Hence $g' > 0$ on $t > 0$ and $g(0) < 0$, giving exactly one positive root t^* . Therefore the decreasing branch $u_+(t)$ reaches $u = 0$ at the unique point $x^* = a t^*$ on the positive real axis.

Step 7 (Increasing branch does not reach the real axis). The increasing branch $u_-(t)$ satisfies $u_-(t) > 0$ for all $t > 1$. Indeed, at $t = 1$ one has $u_- = r^2 > 0$, and $\Delta_u > 0$ with $u_- \geq r^2$ keeps the branch bounded away from zero, so this branch does not cross the real axis.

Conclusion. Combining Steps 2–7: $K(A)$ crosses the positive real axis exactly once (at x^*), giving $n(+\sqrt{v_+}) = 1$. The other three saddles have intersection number zero, as follows. For $-\sqrt{v_+}$ ($= -A$) and $+\sqrt{v_-}$ ($= \bar{A}$), one has $h > 0$ (from $h(-N) = -h(N)$ and $h(\bar{A}) = -h(A)$, with $h(A) < 0$); since $C_0 \subset \{h = 0\}$ and the ascending flow cannot decrease h , these thimbles never reach C_0 .

For $-\sqrt{v_-}$ ($= -\bar{A}$), which has $h < 0$, the imaginary-axis reflection $\sigma : N \mapsto -\bar{N}$ (under which $h \mapsto h$ and $v \mapsto -v$) maps A to $-\bar{A}$ and sends the positive-real-axis crossing of $K(A)$ to a negative-real-axis crossing; hence $K(-\bar{A})$ does not meet C_0 , giving

$$n(-\sqrt{v_-}) = 0. \quad \square$$

Fig. 7: Geometric structure of the proof of Proposition 2 ($\Lambda = 3.1, k = q_1 = 1$). The level curve $P(x, y) = 0$ (red) cannot cross the imaginary axis, since $P(0, y) = -v_A y^2 \neq 0$ (blue band); hence the right and left half-planes are disjoint and $K(A)$ never reaches the negative real axis. At the contributing saddle $A = +\sqrt{v_+}$ the curve has a double point ($t = 1$; inset), from which two branches of the ascending thimble leave: the decreasing branch u_+ (green) descends to a single point $x^* \approx 0.686$ on the positive real axis (C_0), while the increasing branch u_- (purple) satisfies $u_- > 0$ and never returns to the real axis. This unique intersection with C_0 gives $n(A) = 1$; the mirror saddle $B = \sigma(A)$ and the non-contributing pair $\pm\sqrt{v_-}$ yield zero.

8. Discussion

This section places the results of the present paper in the context of prior work, discusses the limitations of the minisuperspace framework, and identifies open problems.

8.1 Relations to Prior Work

The following subsections compare the discriminant structure of the present paper with related work in the literature.

8.1.1 Critical Value and the Discriminant [1, 2]

The no-boundary proposal of Hartle and Hawking [1] is the physical setting of the present analysis. Within its Lorentzian implementation, Feldbrugge et al. [2] noted the critical value $\Lambda_c = 3k/q_1$ as the boundary between classical and quantum phases, but did not formulate the saddle structure in terms of a discriminant D , nor identify the cancellation of the Λ^2 terms as a consequence of the no-boundary condition. The present paper shows that the saddle merger at $\Lambda = \Lambda_c$ and the emergence of the bifurcation parameter Φ are both governed by the discriminant D , which provides a comprehensive description of the Picard–Lefschetz topology and the saddle bifurcation within the minisuperspace framework.

8.1.2 Feldbrugge–Lehners–Turok 2017 [2, 3]

Feldbrugge et al. [2, 3] concluded that the inverse-Gaussian distribution represents a serious problem for the no-boundary proposal. Di Tucci and Lehners [4, 5] proposed an alternative by abandoning $q_0 = 0$ in favor of Robin boundary conditions. The present work retains $q_0 = 0$ and reinterprets the inverse-Gaussian instability as a mathematical consequence of the saddle-bifurcation structure connected to the discriminant condition.

8.1.3 Kontsevich–Segal–Witten Admissibility Criterion [10, 11, 12]

The KSW admissibility criterion [10, 11] provides a condition for the admissibility of complex metrics (off-shell structure); its applications to cosmology have been developed further in [12, 13]. The discriminant structure described in this paper is independent of the KSW criterion. The two are complementary; the analysis of Lehners [12] treats saddle-point behavior under the KSW criterion but does not discuss the connection to saddle mergers.

8.1.4 Moffat 1993 [9]

Moffat [9] derived the generation of time as a bifurcation at a critical temperature T_c . The saddle-bifurcation structure of the present paper is formally analogous but mechanistically different; the primary focus here is the analysis of Picard–Lefschetz geometry. The complexification of the saddle for $D < 0$ is also reminiscent of signature-change scenarios in cosmology [6, 7, 8], although the present mechanism is purely a property of the minisuperspace saddle structure.

8.1.5 Limitations of the Minisuperspace Framework

All results of the present paper are restricted to the minisuperspace framework. Three limitations apply:

First, the assumption of homogeneity and isotropy. Whether $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ and the discriminant structure described here survive when inhomogeneous modes are included remains unexamined.

Second, the semiclassical approximation. The saddle-point method evaluates contributions in the semiclassical limit $\hbar \rightarrow 0$; the corresponding objects in full quantum gravity are not clear.

Third, the relation to the full gravitational path integral. The framework of [10, 11, 12] offers insights into the extension of the Picard–Lefschetz structure to the full theory, but this lies beyond the scope of the present paper.

Within these limitations, the results of the present paper provide a discriminant description of the saddle structure that is internally consistent within the semiclassical minisuperspace approximation. Whether the organizing role of D extends beyond minisuperspace—to inhomogeneous perturbations or to the full gravitational path integral—remains an open question.

8.1.6 Physical Interpretation of the $D < 0$ Complex Saddle

For $D < 0$ ($\Lambda > \Lambda_c$), Proposition 2 establishes that the contributing saddle $N_s = +\sqrt{v_+}$ is complex, with $\text{Re}(N_s) = a > 0$ and $\text{Im}(N_s) = b > 0$. Consequently, the conformal-time increment satisfies $\Delta\tau = N_s \Delta t$, which now has a non-zero real part: $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = a \Delta t > 0$. This is qualitatively distinct from the $D > 0$ regime, in which $N_s = iy_s$ is purely imaginary and $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$. The departure from purely imaginary time is measured by the bifurcation parameter $\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s) = a$, which grows as $\Phi \propto (\Lambda - \Lambda_c)^{1/2}$ (§7.2, Eq. (10)), providing a smooth order-parameter description of the transition.

Several observations can be made within the minisuperspace framework. First, $n(N_s) = 1$ is preserved across the transition (Proposition 2), so the complex saddle contributes to the path integral with the same topological weight as its purely imaginary counterpart in the $D > 0$ regime. Second, the Morse value $h(N_s) < 0$ remains negative throughout $D < 0$ (as the saddle is identified as the unique contributing saddle by Proposition 2), so the exponential suppression of the Lorentzian amplitude is retained. Third, the complex geometry of the saddle modifies the perturbation spectrum: since N_s acquires a real part, the effective action evaluated at the saddle is no longer purely imaginary, which affects the oscillatory versus suppressed character of mode contributions. The precise connection to the CMB large-angle power spectrum is open problem (5) of §8.2.

8.2 Open Problems

- (1) Formal identification of $q_0 = 0$ as the topological boundary $a = 0 \leftrightarrow a > 0$.
- (2) Construction of a physical link between the field rotation of the perturbation sector (§6) and the background result $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$.
- (3) Cosmological interpretation of the complex contributing saddle and the resulting $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) \neq 0$ for $\Lambda > \Lambda_c$, including its relation to the emergence of real (Lorentzian) time.
- (4) The persistence of $n(N_s) = 1$ throughout the $D < 0$ regime, previously accessible only by numerical path-tracing of the gradient flow, is now established analytically in §7.5 (Proposition 2), valid for any finite $\Lambda > \Lambda_c$. The cosmological consequences of the resulting complex contributing saddle, however, remain open (cf. item (3) above).
- (5) Quantitative connection between the exponential suppression of long-wavelength modes implied by $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ and cosmic microwave background (CMB) observations [14].

9. Conclusion

The main results of this paper concern the role of the discriminant in governing not merely the existence of saddles but also the contour selection—the Picard–Lefschetz topology and the identification of the contributing saddle. The results are summarized as follows.

- (i) The single discriminant $D = \beta^2 - 12a/\gamma$ governs both the Picard–Lefschetz topology and the saddle bifurcation as consequences of the no-boundary condition ($q_0 = 0$) (Theorem, §5.6). In particular, D controls not only the existence of saddles but also the determination of the effective intersection number $n(N_s) = 1$ and the identification of the contributing saddle. The three regimes are analytically distinct: $D > 0$ admits a component-structure proof (Lemma 1, Proposition 1, Corollaries 1–3); $D = 0$ marks the saddle merger (the bifurcation threshold); and $D < 0$ requires the global algebraic argument of Proposition 2 (§7.5). All three are organized by D within the minisuperspace framework.
- (ii) $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ was derived from assumptions (A0)–(A5), without invoking the perturbative sector or additional symmetry assumptions.
- (iii) The effective intersection numbers $n(iy_1) = 1$, $n(iy_2) = 0$, and $n(-iy_1) = 0$ were established algebraically within the minisuperspace framework: $n(iy_1) = 1$ via Lemma 1, Proposition 1, Corollaries 1–2 (§5.4) and the uniqueness of the intersection point (§5.5); $n(iy_2) = 0$ via the confinement of $K(iy_2)$ to Component C; and $n(-iy_1) = 0$ via the odd-power symmetry $h(-N) = -h(N)$ (Corollary 3).
- (iv) The deformation of the integration contour into the upper half-plane via the $i\epsilon$ prescription is naturally selected by $\gamma < 0$ (assumption (A2)): $h(x + i\epsilon) < 0$ for small $\epsilon > 0$ supports this deformation direction.
- (v) The real part $\Phi = \text{Re}(N_s)$ emerges through the branch rotation in which \sqrt{D} becomes imaginary and the saddle rotates into the complex plane as D passes below zero, with leading-order scaling $\Phi \propto (\Lambda - \Lambda_c)^{1/2}$ (exponent 1/2, semiclassical approximation, Eqs. (8)–(10) of §7.2). In the $D < 0$ regime the contributing saddle $N_s = +\sqrt{v_+}$ is complex; $n(N_s) = 1$ is established analytically (Proposition 2, §7.5), so the integration contour is maintained, and the conformal-time increment acquires $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) \neq 0$, in contrast to the imaginary-saddle regime $D > 0$.

These results show that the saddle structure of the Lorentzian no-boundary path integral is organized by the single discriminant D . The claims of this paper are limited to the semiclassical minisuperspace framework; extension beyond homogeneity and isotropy and connection to full quantum gravity remain as future work.

Appendix A: Field Rotation in the Perturbation Sector

Under the no-boundary condition $q_0 = 0$, the quadratic action of tensor perturbations φ evaluated at the primary saddle $N_s = iy_s$ takes the form

$$S_2[\varphi] = i\lambda(\omega, N_s) \varphi^2, \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{R},$$

where ω is the wavenumber of the perturbation.

This gives

$$\text{Re}(iS_2/\hbar) = +c_+(\omega, N_s)\varphi^2/\hbar \quad (c_+ > 0),$$

which diverges as $|\varphi| \rightarrow \infty$. This is the inverse-Gaussian distribution of Feldbrugge et al. [2, 3].

Under the formal field rotation $\varphi = i\psi$ ($\psi \in \mathbb{R}$), the term $\varphi^2 \rightarrow -\psi^2$ changes sign, so the exponent of the integrand becomes $\text{Re}(iS_2/\hbar) = -c_+\psi^2/\hbar$, and the integrand becomes Gaussian, $e^{-c_+\psi^2/\hbar}$.

Remark. This field rotation is a formal operation analogous to Wick rotation; it does not imply gauge symmetry or a conserved charge. It reflects the sign behavior of the quadratic form φ^2 under the formal rotation. The justification for this operation, and how it connects to the saddle structure of the background-field (N) space—in particular its physical relation to the background result $\text{Re}(\Delta\tau) = 0$ —is left as a future problem (§8.2(2)).

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